

Perspective comparison of a polished packaging of Hispanic or Latino cultural product to its less polished designed version.

Jeronimo Restrepo

Information Technology and Software Engineering

Physics

Suchith Shantharaj

May 30, 2025

Background:

Hispanic products that are commonly used by Hispanic cultures tend to have a less polished design in comparison to many American (Non-Hispanic) products that tend to have a minimalistic design with sans serif fonts, clean cuts, and a small color palette (Berlin Packaging, 2024; Fessenden 2021). The use of minimalist product design has revolutionized these products in the way they are portrayed to the public as consumers prefer to buy minimalistic-looking products as they give a premium feel (Berlin Packaging, 2024). However, these minimalistic designs may not mimic the same level of trust that outdated or older designs have associated with them when it comes to these cultural products. Hispanic consumers perception on the different versions of these product may be vary due to the cultural association in comparison to non-Hispanic. Hispanic association with the product may be an indicative of trusting the products look over the minimalistic version.

The rise of minimalistic trends involves the loss of color throughout many industries as color palettes appear less broad and rather become more towards black, white, gray and its shades, which is largely attributed to the *McDonaldisation* of society (Hsiao, 2024). However, common observations observe that less corporate Hispanic products tend to have less of a polished design, not being necessarily consistent on their design and but the product remains supplied. Will the unpolished design product convey more trust than the minimalistic version of the product?

Methodology

A total of 35-39 test subjects will receive seven forms, including the demographics. Test subjects are required to complete demographics to then complete the other forms. Each form has 8 questions. The first question is locked, which it does not move place but randomizes from left to right. The first question had the selection of products using an identifier such as the color of the label to distinct them from each other to avoid familiarity bias by preventing the use of the brand name. The remaining questions were in a randomized order to prevent any visual bias as each form has the same questions. Each product had their brand covered and net weigh covered if amount was significant.

Demographics data was mentioned to be confidential and strictly for research purposes.

Around 24 participants were asked if they wanted to participate in research regarding product packaging. Participants were informed that answers were independent. Each person saw the demographics QR code first and were indicated to complete it before continuing. After filling the demographic, subjects were shown three sheets of paper that had two QR codes folded in half. Each QR code was labeled at the top with its respective name. Each person was given a set (referring to sheet with two QR codes) to complete and each set was completed randomly to achieve a total completion of seven product QR code forms and the demographics form.

Remaining participants (around 15) answered the forms from a post on Homeroom Chats (Bulletin Board for 4 graduating classes) on which they were told they would be answering questions on different versions of a product and were instructed to complete all the forms as there were no right

or wrong answers. A title was given for each form link respective to its name, with demographics being first and bolded.

Each form (excluding demographics) consisted of seven multiple choice regarding which one they would buy, their cultural connection with the product they chose, their cultural connection with the product they did not choose, belief if they would receive quality with their choice, cultural authenticity of their choice, cultural authenticity of the product they did not chose, and an open ended feeling or opinion about the product they did not chose.

Results

For rating questions, graph follows the followed colors

1 Being Lowest; 5 Highest

- 5- Pink
- 4-Blue
- 3- Green
- 2 – Red
- 1- Yellow

Vegetable Condiments

35 Participants saw these two products when answering on **Vegetable Condiments**

Purple on Bottom Label

Vegetables on Label

Gender

Green - Woman : 19
 Pink - Man: 14
 Man and Woman - Blue: 1
 Non-Binary - Orange: 1

Age Groups

Pink - 16-18: 28
 Orange - 25-30: 2
 Purple - 61-65: 3
 Red - 46-50: 1
 Blue - 56-60: 1
 Green - 13-15: 1

Total Responses- 35

Red - Purple on Bottom Label
 Blue - Vegetables on Label

Blue - Less Polished Design: 27
 Red - Minimal Design: 8

Races of Participants

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 12
 Orange - Black: 7
 Cyan - White: 7
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2
 Pink - Black and White: 2
 Yellow - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander and White: 1
 Prefer not to answer: 1

Participants that Identified as Hispanic or Latino - 17

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 12
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2

18/35 Participants did not Identified as Hispanic or Latino

17/35 Participants Identified as Hispanic or Latino

Purchasability of Vegetable Condiments by group

Hispanic or Latinos

Non-Hispanic or Latinos

Hispanic or Latino Responses

Responses from Vegetables on Label

Responses from Purple on Label

**Connection with Purple
on Label Product 1-5, 1
Being lowest; 5 Highest
17 Responses**

5: 0 Participants
Blue - 4: 3 Participants
Green - 3: 6 Participants
Red - 2: 2 Participants
Yellow 1- : 6 Participants

**Cultural Authenticity of
Chosen Product: Purple
on Bottom on Label
5 Selections**

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
Blue - 4: 3 Participants
Green - 3: 1 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

**Receiving Quality from
Chosen Product: Purple
on Bottom Label
5 Selections**

Yellow - Yes: 3 Participants
Green - Maybe: 1 Participants
Red - No: 1 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses

Responses from Vegetable on Product

**Connection with Vegetable Label on Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses**

Pink - 5: 4 Participants
 Blue - 4: 7 Participants
 Green - 3: 1 Participants
 Red - 2: 1 Participants
 Yellow 1- : 5 Participants

**Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Vegetables on Label
15 Selections**

Pink - 5: 4 Participants
 Blue - 4: 4 Participants
 Green - 3: 4 Participants
 Red - 2: 2 Participants
 Yellow 1- : 1 Participants

**Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Vegetables on Label
15 Responses**

Yellow - Yes: 13 Participants
 Green - Maybe: 2 Participants
 No: 0 Participants

Responses from Purple on Bottom Label Product

**Connection with Purple on Label Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses**

5: 0 Participants
 4: 0 Participants
 Green - 3: 7 Participants
 Red - 2: 5 Participants
 Yellow 1- : 6 Participants

**Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Purple on Bottom on Label
3 Selections**

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
 4: 0 Participants
 Green - 3: 2 Participants
 2: 0 Participants
 1: 0 Participants

**Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Purple on Bottom Label
3 Selections**

Yellow - Yes: 1 Participants
 Green - Maybe: 2 Participants
 No: 0 Participants

Non- Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Vegetables on Label from Participants that chose Purple on Label

“I guess I have a bias that if it has Spanish on the packaging and it’s a vegetable condiment (like a salsa) I would be more inclined to pick it over something that has English words.”

Remarks on Purple on Label from Participants that chose Vegetables on Label

“Cute but would go for cheaper”

“seems white washed”

“seems corporate”

“I thought it was cute but I would usually go for the cheaper option, which would most likely be the second one.”

“plain”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (17 Participants)

Remarks on Vegetables on Label from Participants that chose Purple on Label

“less tasty”

“little boring”

“doesn’t look good”

Remarks on Purple on Label from Participants that chose Vegetables on Label

“looks so empty”

“doesn't look home made”

“watered down white people brand”

“it might be a good but I like that I can see the vegetables on it.”

Churros

36 Participants saw these two products when answering to **Churros**

Yellow Background

Grey Background

Total Responses- 36

Grey - Grey Background
Yellow - Yellow Background

Grey - Grey Background: 18
Yellow - Yellow Background: 18

Gender

Green - Woman : 20
Pink - Man: 14
Man and Woman - Blue: 1
Non-Binary - Orange: 1

Age Groups

Pink - 16-18: 29
Orange - 25-30: 2
Purple - 61-65: 3
Red - 46-50: 1
Blue - 56-60: 1
Green - 13-15: 1

Races of Participants

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 13
 Orange - Black: 7
 Cyan - White: 7
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2
 Pink - Black and White: 2
 Yellow - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander and White: 1
 Prefer not to answer: 1

18/36 Participants
 did not Identified
 as Hispanic or
 Latino

Participants that Identified as Hispanic or Latino - 18

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 13
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2

18/36 Participants
 Identified as
 Hispanic or Latino

Purchasability of Churros by group

Hispanics or Latinos

Non-Hispanic or Latinos

Hispanic or Latinos

Purchasability of Products

Yellow- Yellow Background: 13
 Participants
 Grey - Grey Background : 5 Participants

Non- Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products (18)

Yellow - Yellow Background: 5 Participants
 Grey - Grey Background : 13 Participants

Hispanic or Latino Responses

Responses from Yellow Background

Connection with Yellow Background on Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 5 Participants
Blue - 4: 6 Participants
Green - 3: 3 Participants
Red - 2: 2 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 2 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Yellow Background
13 Selections

Pink - 5: 5 Participants
Blue - 4: 4 Participants
Green - 3: 4 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Yellow Background
13 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 8 Participants
Green - Maybe: 4 Participants
Red - No: 1 Participants

Responses from Grey Background

Connection with Grey Background Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

5: 0 Participants
Blue - 4: 2 Participants
Green - 3: 7 Participants
Red - 2: 3 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 6 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Grey Background
5 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 3 Participants
Green - Maybe: 1 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Grey Background 5 Selections

5 : 0 Participants
 Blue - 4 : 1 Participants
 Green - 3 : 1 Participants
 Red - 2 : 2 Participants
 Yellow - 1 : 1 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses

Responses from Yellow Background

**Connection with Yellow
Background 1-5, 1 Being
lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses**

5: 0 Participants
 Blue - 4 : 2 Participants
 Green - 3 : 7 Participants
 Red - 2 : 4 Participants
 Yellow - 1 : 5 Participants

**Cultural Authenticity
of Chosen Product:
Yellow Background
5 Selections**

5: 0 Participants
 Blue - 4 : 2 Participants
 Green - 3 : 3 Participants
 2 : 0 Participants
 1 - : 0 Participants

**Receiving Quality from
Chosen Product: Yellow
Background
5 Responses**

Yellow - Yes: 4 Participants
 Green - Maybe: 1 Participants
 No: 0 Participants

Responses from Grey Background

Connection with Grey Background 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 3 Participants
Blue - 4: 3 Participants
Green - 3: 5 Participants
Red - 2: 3 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 4 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Grey Background
13 Selections

Pink - 5: 3 Participants
Blue - 4: 3 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
Red - 2: 2 Participants
Yellow - 1: 3 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Grey Background
13 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 7 Participants
Green - Maybe: 4 Participants
Red - No: 2 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Yellow Background from Participants that chose Grey Background

“Seems like an older product design”

Remarks on Grey Background from Participants that chose Yellow Background

“It doesn't look authentic compared to the other one”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Yellow Background from Participants that chose Grey Background

“It may be lower quality, it may look a little more culturally better choice but the packaging looks better in the one I chose”

Remarks on Grey Background from Participants that chose Yellow Background

“it looks not very tasty, packaging give me an american vibe”

“I feel like it's more Americanized ”

Sour Cream

37 Participants saw these two products when answering to **Sour Cream**

White Background

Red Background

Total Responses- 37

Red - Red Background
Grey - White Background

Red - Red Background: 22
Grey - White Background: 15

Gender

Green - Woman : 21
Pink - Man: 14
Man and Woman - Blue: 1
Non-Binary - Orange: 1

Age Groups

Pink - 16-18: 29
Orange - 25-30: 2
Purple - 61-65: 2
Cyan - 36-40: 1
Red - 46-50: 1
Blue - 56-60: 1
Green - 13-15: 1

Races of Participants

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 13
 Orange - Black: 7
 Cyan - White: 7
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2
 Pink - Black and White: 2
 Yellow - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander and White: 1
 Prefer not to answer: 1
 Grey - Asian: 1

Participants that Identified as Hispanic or Latino -

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 13
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2

19/37 Participants did not Identified as Hispanic or Latino

18/37 Participants did not Identified as Hispanic or Latino

Purchasability of Sour Cream by group

Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products

Red - Red Background: 8 Participants
 Grey - White Background : 10 Participants

Non- Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products (19)

Red - Red Background: 14 Participants
 Grey - White Background : 5 Participants

Hispanic or Latino Responses

White Background

Connection with White on Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 6 Participants
Blue - 4: 3 Participants
Green - 3: 3 Participants
Red - 2: 1 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 5 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: White Background
10 Selections

Pink- 5: 5 Participants
Blue - 4: 2 Participants
Green - 3: 3 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: White Background
10 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 8 Participants
Green - Maybe: 1 Participants
Red - No: 1 Participants

Red Background

Connection with Red Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
Blue - 4: 2 Participants
Green - 3: 6 Participants
Red - 2: 5 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 4 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Red Background
8 Selections

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
Blue - 4: 3 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
Red - 2: 1 Participants
Yellow - 1: 1 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Red Background
8 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 4 Participants
Green - Maybe: 4 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses

White Background

Connection with White Background 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
19 Responses

Pink - 5: 4 Participants
Blue - 4: 2 Participants
Green - 3: 1 Participants
Red - 2: 5 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 7 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: White Background
5 Selections

5: 3 Participants
Blue - 4: 2 Participants
3: 0 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: White Background
5 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 4 Participants
Green - Maybe: 1 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Red Background

Connection with Red Background 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
19 Responses

Pink - 5: 3 Participants
Blue - 4: 6 Participants
Green - 3: 3 Participants
Red - 2: 5 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 2 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Red Background
14 Selections

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
4: 0 Participants
Green - 3: 6 Participants
Red - 2: 3 Participants
Yellow - 1: 4 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Red Background
14 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 10 Participants
Green - Maybe: 4 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (19 Participants)

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Red Background

“seems more authentic, might have a slightly less processed taste”

Remarks on Red Background from Participants that chose White Background

“The other one looks like store branded. Sour cream you’d probably get in Stop&Shop or Shoprite.”

“This one is usually a product I see most people who come from an American background have or buy compared to the other option”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Red Background

“i like the name or label of it but i would rather have the all natural version”

Remarks on Red Background from Participants that chose White Background

“I feel that the label is very plain and it makes it look like it wont taste well. ”

Can of Beans

36 Participants saw these two products when answering to **Can of Beans**

Blue Background

White Background

Total Responses- 36

Orange - White Background
Blue - Blue Background

Orange - White Background: 8
Blue - Blue Background: 28

Gender

Green - Woman : 20
Pink - Man: 14
Man and Woman - Blue: 1
Non-Binary - Orange: 1

Age Groups

Pink - 16-18: 29
Orange - 25-30: 2
Purple - 61-65: 2
Red - 46-50: 1
Blue - 56-60: 1
Green - 13-15: 1

Races of Participants

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 13
 Orange - Black: 7
 Cyan - White: 7
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2
 Pink - Black and White: 2
 Yellow - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander and White: 1
 Prefer not to answer: 1

18/36 Participants did not Identified as Hispanic or Latino

Participants that Identified as Hispanic or Latino - 18

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 13
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2

18/36 Participants Identified as Hispanic or Latino

Purchasability of Can of Beans by Group

Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products

Blue - Blue Background: 17 Participants
 Orange - White Background : 1 Participants

Non- Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products (18)

Blue - Blue Background: 7 Participants
 Orange - White Background : 11 Participants

Hispanic or Latino Responses

Blue Background

Connection with Blue Background Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 6 Participants
Blue - 4: 7 Participants
Green - 3: 3 Participants
2: 0 Participants
Yellow 1- : 2 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Blue Background
17 Selections

Pink- 5: 5 Participants
Blue - 4: 7 Participants
Green - 3: 4 Participants
2: 0 Participants
Yellow - 1: 1 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Blue Background

17 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 12 Participants
Green - Maybe: 4 Participants
Red - No: 1 Participants

White Background

Connection with White Background Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

5: 0 Participants
Blue - 4: 1 Participants
Green - 3: 4 Participants
Red - 2: 6 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 7 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: White Background
1 Selections

5: 0 Participants
4: 0 Participants
Green - 3: 1 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: White Background
1 Selections

Yes: 0 Participants
Maybe: 0 Participants
No: 1 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses

Blue Background

Connection with Blue Background 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
Blue - 4: 6 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
Red - 2: 1 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 8 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Blue Background
11 Selections

Pink 5: 2 Participants
Blue - 4: 6 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
Red - 2: 1 Participants
1 : 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Blue Background
11 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 9 Participants
Green - Maybe: 2 Participants
No: 0 Participants

White Background

Connection with White Background 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

5: 0 Participants
Blue - 4: 3 Participants
3: 0 Participants
Red - 2: 6 Participants
Yellow 1 - : 9 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: White Background
7 Selections

5: 0 Participants
Blue 4: 1 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
Red - 2: 1 Participants
Yellow - 1: 3 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: White Background
7 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 3 Participants
Green - Maybe: 3 Participants
Red - No: 1 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

No Remarks on Blue Background from Participants that chose White Background

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Blue Background

“I’m pretty sure that’s from Whole Foods... I’d rather something more authentic”

“It seems corporate and like it’s from Walmart”

“It looks like it would taste bland”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Blue background from Participants that chose White Background

“It looked cheaper”

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Blue Background

“It’s feels more like home”

“If I am going to buy a Hispanic product, I would like it to be represented by the language as well. The white background has only English on it.”

“I think it just I’m not used to eating that one cause I grow up with the other one”

“I’d choose it but the other product is visually more attractive to me”

“I like the colors but I’m more familiar with cans that look like the blue can”

Plantain Chips

38 Participants saw these two products when answering to **Plantain Chips**

Red Swirls

Green Background

Total Responses- 38

Green - Green Background
Red - Red Swirls

Green - Green Background: 8
Red - Red Swirls: 30

Gender

Green - Woman : 21
Pink - Man: 15
Man and Woman - Blue: 1
Non-Binary - Orange: 1

Age Groups

Pink - 16-18: 30
Orange - 25-30: 2
Purple - 61-65: 2
Cyan - 36 - 40: 1
Red - 46-50: 1
Blue - 56-60: 1
Green - 13-15: 1

Races of Participants

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 15
 Orange - Black: 7
 Cyan - White: 7
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2
 Pink - Black and White: 2
 Yellow - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander and White: 1
 Prefer not to answer: 1

18/38 Participants did not Identified as Hispanic or Latino

Participants that Identified as Hispanic or Latino - 20

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 15
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2

20/38 Participants Identified as Hispanic or Latino

Purchasability of Plantain Chips by group

Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products

Red - Red Swirls: 17 Participants
 Green - Green Background : 3 Participants

Non- Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products (18)

Red - Red Swirls: 13 Participants
 Green - Green Background : 5 Participants

Hispanic or Latino Responses

Red Swirls

Connection with Red Swirls Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
20 Responses

Pink - 5: 8 Participants
Blue - 4: 6 Participants
Green - 3: 3 Participants
2: 0 Participants
Yellow 1- : 3 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product:
Red Swirls
17 Selections

Pink- 5: 9 Participants
Blue - 4: 6 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Red Swirls Background
17 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 15 Participants
Green - Maybe: 2 Participants
No: - Participants

Green Background

**Connection with Green Background Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
20 Responses**

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
Blue - 4: 2 Participants
Green - 3: 6 Participants
Red - 2: 6 Participants
Yellow 1- : 5 Participants

**Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Green Background
3 Selections**

Pink -5: 1 Participants
4: 0 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

**Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Green Background
3 Selections**

Yellow - Yes: 1 Participants
Maybe: 2 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses

Red Swirls

Connection with Red Swirls
1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 2 Participants
Blue - 4: 4 Participants
Green - 3: 3 Participants
Red - 2: 1 Participants
Yellow 1- : 8 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Red Swirls
13 Selections

Pink 5: 2 Participants
Blue - 4: 5 Participants
Green - 3: 4 Participants
2: 0 Participants
Yellow - 1: 2 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Red Swirls Background
13 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 8 Participants
Green - Maybe: 4 Participants
Red - No: 1 Participants

Green Background

Connection with Green Background
1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
18 Responses

Pink - 5: 2 Participants
4: 0 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
Red - 2: 4 Participants
Yellow 1- : 10 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Green Background
5 Selections

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
4: 0 Participants
Green - 3: 1 Participants
Red - 2: 2 Participants
Yellow - 1: 1 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Green Background
5 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 2 Participants
Green - Maybe: 3 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Red Swirls from Participants that chose Green Background

“It probably tastes good and is an authentic product but I wouldn't know because Im not a fan of the flavor”

Remarks on Green Background from Participants that chose Red Swirls

“It seems like it wouldn't taste as good as the bag on the right [Red Swirls] looks a little more authentic to its Caribbean culture.”

“It seems very modern and corporate ”

“They don't look as authentic ”

“seems more processed, less authentic, might taste blander ”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (20 Participants)

No Remarks on Red Swirls from Participants that chose Green Background

Remarks on Green Background from Participants that chose Red Swirls

“it looks very disgusting and plain packaging, looks like something that they would sell at trader joe's ”

“It's too Americanized ”

“it looks like the white people version cuz of the packaging”

Flour Tortillas

39 Participants saw these two products when answering to **Flour Tortillas**

White Circle

Teal Background

Total Responses- 39

Grey - White Background
Teal - Teal Background

Grey - White Circle: 30
Teal - Teal Background: 9

Gender

Green - Woman : 22
Pink - Man: 15
Man and Woman - Blue: 1
Non-Binary - Orange: 1

Age Groups

Pink - 16-18: 31
Orange - 25-30: 2
Purple - 61-65: 2
Cyan - 36 - 40: 1
Red - 46-50: 1
Blue - 56-60: 1
Green - 13-15: 1

Races of Participants

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 14
 Orange - Black: 8
 Cyan - White: 8
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2
 Pink - Black and White: 1
 Yellow - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander and White: 1
 Grey - Asian: 1
 Prefer not to answer: 1

Participants that Identified as Hispanic or Latino - 19

Blue - Hispanic or Latino: 14
 Red - White Hispanic: 3
 Green - Black Hispanic or Latino: 2

20/39 Participants did not Identified as Hispanic or Latino

19/39 Participants did not Identified as Hispanic or Latino

Purchasability of Flour Tortillas by Group

Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products

Grey - White Circle: 16 Participants
 Green - Green Background : 3 Participants

Non- Hispanic or Latinos Purchasability of Products (20)

Grey - White Circle: 14 Participants
 Teal - Teal Background : 6 Participants

Hispanic or Latino Responses

White Circle

**Connection with White
Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest;
5 Highest
19 Responses**

Pink - 5: 7 Participants
Blue - 4: 9 Participants
Green - 3: 1 Participants
Red- 2: 1 Participants
Yellow 1- : 1 Participants

**Cultural Authenticity
of Chosen Product:
White Circle
16 Selections**

Pink- 5: 7 Participants
Blue - 4: 5 Participants
Green - 3: 2 Participants
Red- 2: 2 Participants
1: 0 Participants

**Receiving Quality from
Chosen Product: White
Circle**

16 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 13 Participants
Green - Maybe: 3 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Teal Background

Connection with Teal Background Product 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
19 Responses

Pink - 5: 2 Participants
Blue - 4: 2 Participants
Green - 3: 1 Participants
Red - 2: 5 Participants
Yellow 1- : 9 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Teal Background
3 Selections

Pink -5: 1 Participants
Blue- 4: 2 Participants
3: 0 Participants
2: 0 Participants
1: 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Teal Background
3 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 2 Participants
Green - Maybe: 1 Participants
No: 0 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Response

White Circle

Connection with White Circle 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
20 Responses

Pink - 5: 3 Participants
 Blue - 4: 6 Participants
 Green - 3: 6 Participants
 Red - 2: 2 Participants
 Yellow 1 - : 3 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: White Circle
14 Selections

Pink 5: 4 Participants
 Blue - 4: 1 Participants
 Green - 3: 5 Participants
 Red - 2: 3 Participants
 Yellow - 1: 1 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: White Circle
14 Selections

Yellow - Yes: 9 Participants
 Green - Maybe: 5 Participants
 No: 0 Participants

Teal Background

Connection with teal Background 1-5, 1 Being lowest; 5 Highest
20 Responses

Pink - 5: 1 Participants
 Blue - 4: 2 Participants
 Green - 3: 6 Participants
 Red - 2: 6 Participants
 Yellow 1 - : 5 Participants

Cultural Authenticity of Chosen Product: Teal Background
6 Selections

Pink - 5: 3 Participants
 4: 0 Participants
 Green - 3: 2 Participants
 Red - 2: 1 Participants
 1: 0 Participants

Receiving Quality from Chosen Product: Teal Background
6 Responses

Yellow - Yes: 5 Participants
 Green - Maybe: 1 Participants
 No: 0 Participants

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (20 Participants)

Remarks on White Circle from Participants that chose Teal Background

“They look like they’re trying too hard for a Mexican audience, “taste of Mexico” is cringe”

Remarks on Teal Background from Participants that chose White Circle

“It probably wouldn't taste as good and it looks more authentic to the true flavors“

“It looks like it’s authentic”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (19 Participants)

No Remarks on White Circle from Participants that chose Teal Background

Remarks on Teal Background from Participants that chose White Circle

“They don look good based in the label. ”

“they look like they aren’t authentic ”

“nothing really I just gravitate towards packaging like the white circle one”

Analysis

Vegetable Condiments

12/17 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Vegetables on Label product

5/17 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Purple on Bottom Label product

15/18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Vegetable on Condiment.

3/18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Purple on Bottom Label

Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

17 Hispanic or Latino Connection with **Vegetables on Label**

6 Rated product a 5

6 Rated product a 4

1 Rated product a 3

2 Rated product a 2

2 Rated product a 1

17 Hispanic or Latino Connection with **Purple on Label**

0 Rated product a 5

3 Rated product a 4

6 Rated product a 3

2 Rated product a 2

6 Rated product a 1

12 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **Vegetable on Label**

4 Rated product a 5

4 Rated product a 4

2 Rated product a 3

2 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

5 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **Purple on Bottom Label**

1 Rated product a 5

3 Rated product a 4

1 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino Connection with **Vegetable Label**

- 4 Rated product a 5
- 7 Rated product a 4
- 1 Rated product a 3
- 1 Rated product a 2
- 5 Rated product a 1

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino Connection with **Purple on Label Product**

- 0 Rated product a 5
- 0 Rated product a 4
- 7 Rated product a 3
- 5 Rated product a 2
- 6 Rated product a 1

15 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Vegetable on Label**

- 4 Rated product a 5
- 4 Rated product a 4
- 4 Rated product a 3
- 2 Rated product a 2
- 1 Rated product a 1

3 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Purple on Bottom Label**

- 1 Rated product a 5
- 0 Rated product a 4
- 2 Rated product a 3
- 0 Rated product a 2
- 1 Rated product a 1

Non- Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Vegetables on Label from Participants that chose Purple on Label

“I guess I have a bias that if it has **Spanish** on the packaging and it’s a vegetable condiment (like a salsa) I would be more inclined to pick it over something that has **English** words.”

Remarks on Purple on Label from Participants that chose Vegetables on Label

“Cute but would go for **cheaper**”

“seems **white washed**”

“seems **corporate**”

“I thought it was cute but I would usually go for the **cheaper option, which would most likely be the second one.**”

“plain”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (17 Participants)

Remarks on Vegetables on Label from Participants that chose Purple on Label

“less tasty”

“little boring”

“doesn’t look good”

Remarks on Purple on Label from Participants that chose Vegetables on Label

“looks so empty”

“doesn't look **home made**”

“watered down **white people brand**”

“it might be a good but I like that I can see the vegetables on it.”

Churros

13/18 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Yellow Background product

5/18 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Grey Background product

5/18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Yellow Background

13/18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Grey Background

Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

18 Hispanic or Latino Connection with Yellow Background

5 Rated product a 5

6 Rated product a 4

3 Rated product a 3

2 Rated product a 2

2 Rated product a 1

18 Hispanic or Latino Connection with Grey Background

0 Rated product a 5

2 Rated product a 4

7 Rated product a 3

3 Rated product a 2

6 Rated product a 1

13 Hispanic or Latino Cultural authenticity with chosen product: Yellow Background

5 Rated product a 5

4 Rated product a 4

4 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

5 Hispanic or Latino Cultural authenticity with chosen product: Grey Background

0 Rated product a 5

1 Rated product a 4

1 Rated product a 3

2 Rated product a 2

1 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino Connection with **Yellow Background**

- 0 Rated product a 5
- 2 Rated product a 4
- 7 Rated product a 3
- 4 Rated product a 2
- 5 Rated product a 1

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino Connection with **Grey Background**

- 3 Rated product a 5
- 3 Rated product a 4
- 5 Rated product a 3
- 3 Rated product a 2
- 4 Rated product a 1

5 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Yellow Background**

- 0 Rated product a 5
- 2 Rated product a 4
- 3 Rated product a 3
- 0 Rated product a 2
- 0 Rated product a 1

13 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Grey Background**

- 3 Rated product a 5
- 3 Rated product a 4
- 2 Rated product a 3
- 2 Rated product a 2
- 3 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Yellow Background from Participants that chose Grey Background

“Seems like an older product design”

Remarks on Grey Background from Participants that chose Yellow Background

“It doesn't look **authentic** compared to the other one”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Yellow Background from Participants that chose Grey Background

“It may be **lower quality**, it may look a little more **culturally** better choice but the packaging looks better in the one I chose”

Remarks on Grey Background from Participants that chose Yellow Background

“it looks not very tasty, packaging give me **an american** vibe”

“I feel like it's more **Americanized** ”

Sour Cream

10/18 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the White Background product

8/18 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Red Background product

5/19 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the White Background

14/19 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Red Background

Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

18 Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **White Background**

6 Rated product a 5

3 Rated product a 4

3 Rated product a 3

1 Rated product a 2

5 Rated product a 1

18 Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Red Background**

1 Rated product a 5

2 Rated product a 4

6 Rated product a 3

5 Rated product a 2

4 Rated product a 1

10 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **White Background**

5 Rated product a 5

2 Rated product a 4

3 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

8 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **Red Background**

1 Rated product a 5

3 Rated product a 4

2 Rated product a 3

1 Rated product a 2

1 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

19 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **White Background**

- 4 Rated product a 5
- 2 Rated product a 4
- 1 Rated product a 3
- 5 Rated product a 2
- 7 Rated product a 1

19 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Red Background**

- 3 Rated product a 5
- 6 Rated product a 4
- 3 Rated product a 3
- 5 Rated product a 2
- 2 Rated product a 1

5 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **White Background**

- 3 Rated product a 5
- 2 Rated product a 4
- 0 Rated product a 3
- 0 Rated product a 2
- 0 Rated product a 1

14 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Red Background**

- 1 Rated product a 5
- 0 Rated product a 4
- 6 Rated product a 3
- 3 Rated product a 2
- 4 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (19 Participants)

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Red Background

“seems more **authentic**, might have a slightly less processed taste”

Remarks on Red Background from Participants that chose White Background

“The other one looks like store branded. **Sour cream** you’d probably get in **Stop&Shop** or **Shoprite**.”

“This one is usually a product **I see most people who come from an American background** have or buy compared to the other option”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Red Background

“i like the name or label of it but i would rather have the all natural version”

Remarks on Red Background from Participants that chose White Background

“I feel that the label is very plain and it makes it look like it wont taste well. ”

Can of Beans

17/18 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Blue Background product

1/18 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the White Background product

11/18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Blue Background

7 /18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the White Background

Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

18 Hispanic or Latino Connection with Blue Background

6 Rated product a 5

7 Rated product a 4

3 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

2 Rated product a 1

18 Hispanic or Latino Connection with White Background

0 Rated product a 5

1 Rated product a 4

4 Rated product a 3

6 Rated product a 2

7 Rated product a 1

17 Hispanic or Latino Cultural authenticity with chosen product: Blue Background

5 Rated product a 5

7 Rated product a 4

4 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

1 Rated product a 1

1 Hispanic or Latino Cultural authenticity with chosen product: White Background

0 Rated product a 5

0 Rated product a 4

1 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Blue Background**

- 1 Rated product a 5
- 6 Rated product a 4
- 2 Rated product a 3
- 1 Rated product a 2
- 8 Rated product a 1

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **White Background**

- 0 Rated product a 5
- 3 Rated product a 4
- 0 Rated product a 3
- 6 Rated product a 2
- 9 Rated product a 1

11 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Blue Background**

- 2 Rated product a 5
- 6 Rated product a 4
- 2 Rated product a 3
- 1 Rated product a 2
- 0 Rated product a 1

7 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **White Background**

- 0 Rated product a 5
- 1 Rated product a 4
- 2 Rated product a 3
- 1 Rated product a 2
- 3 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

No Remarks on Blue Background from Participants that chose White Background

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Blue Background

“I’m pretty sure that’s from Whole Foods... I’d rather something more authentic”

“It seems corporate and like it’s from Walmart”

“It looks like it would taste bland”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Blue background from Participants that chose White Background

“It looked cheaper”

Remarks on White Background from Participants that chose Blue Background

“It’s feels more like home”

“If I am going to buy a **Hispanic product**, I would like it to be represented by the **language** as well. The white background has only English on it.”

“I think it just I’m not used to eating that one cause **I grow up with the other one**”

“I’d choose it but the other product is visually more attractive to me”

“I like the colors but **I’m more familiar with cans that look like the blue can**”

Plantain Chips

17/20 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Red Swirls product

3/20 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Green Background product

13/18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Red Swirls Background

5/18 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Green Background

Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

20 Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Red Swirls**

8 Rated product a 5

6 Rated product a 4

3 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

3 Rated product a 1

20 Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Green Background**

1 Rated product a 5

2 Rated product a 4

6 Rated product a 3

6 Rated product a 2

5 Rated product a 1

17 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **Red Swirls**

9 Rated product a 5

6 Rated product a 4

2 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

3 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **Green Background**

1 Rated product a 5

0 Rated product a 4

2 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Red Swirls**

- 2 Rated product a 5
- 4 Rated product a 4
- 3 Rated product a 3
- 1 Rated product a 2
- 8 Rated product a 1

18 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Green Background**

- 2 Rated product a 5
- 0 Rated product a 4
- 2 Rated product a 3
- 4 Rated product a 2
- 10 Rated product a 1

13 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Red Swirls**

- 2 Rated product a 5
- 5 Rated product a 4
- 4 Rated product a 3
- 0 Rated product a 2
- 2 Rated product a 1

5 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Green Background**

- 1 Rated product a 5
- 0 Rated product a 4
- 1 Rated product a 3
- 2 Rated product a 2
- 1 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (18 Participants)

Remarks on Red Swirls from Participants that chose Green Background

“It probably tastes good and is an **authentic** product but I wouldn't know because Im not a fan of the flavor”

Remarks on Green Background from Participants that chose Red Swirls

“It seems like it wouldn't taste as good as the bag on the right [Red Swirls] **looks a little more authentic to its Caribbean culture.**”

“It seems **very modern and corporate** ”

“They don't look as **authentic** ”

“seems more processed, less authentic, might **taste blander** ”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (20 Participants)

No Remarks on Red Swirls from Participants that chose Green Background

Remarks on Green Background from Participants that chose Red Swirls

“it looks very disgusting and plain packaging, looks **like something that they would sell at trader joe's** ”

“It's too **Americanized** ”

“it looks like the **white people version cuz of the packaging**”

Flour Tortillas

16/19 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the White Circle product

3/19 Hispanic or Latino participants chose the Teal Background product

14/20 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the White Circle Background

6/20 Non-Hispanic or Latino chose the Teal Background

Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

19 Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **White Circle**

7 Rated product a 5

9 Rated product a 4

1 Rated product a 3

1 Rated product a 2

1 Rated product a 1

19 Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Teal Background**

2 Rated product a 5

2 Rated product a 4

1 Rated product a 3

5 Rated product a 2

9 Rated product a 1

16 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **White Circle**

7 Rated product a 5

5 Rated product a 4

2 Rated product a 3

2 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

3 Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chosen product: **Teal Background**

1 Rated product a 5

2 Rated product a 4

0 Rated product a 3

0 Rated product a 2

0 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Responses to Products

20 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **White Circle**

- 3 Rated product a 5
- 6 Rated product a 4
- 6 Rated product a 3
- 2 Rated product a 2
- 3 Rated product a 1

20 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Connection** with **Teal Background**

- 1 Rated product a 5
- 2 Rated product a 4
- 6 Rated product a 3
- 6 Rated product a 2
- 5 Rated product a 1

14 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **White Circle**

- 4 Rated product a 5
- 1 Rated product a 4
- 5 Rated product a 3
- 3 Rated product a 2
- 1 Rated product a 1

6 Non-Hispanic or Latino **Cultural authenticity** with chose product: **Teal Background**

- 3 Rated product a 5
- 0 Rated product a 4
- 2 Rated product a 3
- 1 Rated product a 2
- 0 Rated product a 1

Non-Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (20 Participants)

Remarks on White Circle from Participants that chose Teal Background

“They look like they’re **trying too hard** for a Mexican audience, “taste of Mexico” is cringe”

Remarks on Teal Background from Participants that chose White Circle

“It probably wouldn't taste as good and it looks **more authentic** to the true flavors“

“It looks like it’s authentic”

Hispanic or Latino Remarks on Products (19 Participants)

No Remarks on White Circle from Participants that chose Teal Background

Remarks on Teal Background from Participants that chose White Circle

“They don look good based in the label. ”

“they look like **they aren’t authentic** ”

“nothing really **I just gravitate towards packaging like the white circle one**”

Conclusion

With the data collected, it is observed that Hispanic or Latino participants would tend to purchase the less polished design in all the products presented. In addition, non-Hispanic participants also responded similarly, with 4/6 of the less polished products having higher purchasability than the polished version.

Hispanic or Latino Conclusions

Hispanic or Latino participants demonstrated High ratings on their connection with the less polished version. In comparison to the polished version of the product on which they presented a Low connection with the product.

Hispanics or Latino participants who chose the less polished version of the product, had High to Neutral cultural authenticity. Participants who chose the polished version, had an overall Neutral cultural authenticity. It is important to note that there were lower Hispanic participants that chose the polished version of the product.

Hispanic or Latino participants that chose the polished version mentioned that the less polished version was boring, lower quality but culturally better, preferred the natural labels, or looked cheaper. It is important to note that there were lower Hispanic participants that chose the polished version of the product.

Hispanic or Latino that chose the less polished version mentioned that the polished version did not look homemade, did not look authentic, associated with white people brand, looks American, too plain, or did not look familiar to the products they grew up with.

Non-Hispanic or Latino Conclusions

Non-Hispanic or Latino Participants demonstrated Neutral to Low connection with the less polished version. Similarly, the polished version demonstrated a Neutral to Low connection with the product by the same group.

Non-Hispanic or Latino that chose the less polished version of the product demonstrated a High to Neutral rating on cultural authenticity. Non-Hispanic or Latino participants who chose the polished version demonstrated Neutral cultural authenticity.

Non-Hispanic or Latino participants that chose the polished version mentioned that the less polished version looked like an older product design, preferred Spanish words for a Hispanic product, seems more authentic and might have a less processed taste, tastes better, and is authentic but do not like the flavor.

Non-Hispanic or Latino participants that chose the less polished version mentioned that the polished version was cute but would go for cheaper, seems whitewashed, corporate, plain, does not look authentic, bland taste, more authentic to Caribbean culture, and very modern.

On cultural products that may not be as culturally connected as others like the Sour Cream or Churros, Non-Hispanic participants chose the polished version. Hispanic or Latino participants still chose the less polished product though more were choosing the polished design unlike on other products that were more culturally connected like the Vegetable Condiments, Churros, Can of Beans, Plantain Chips, and Flour Tortillas.

Hispanic or Latino participants prefer less polished designs on cultural products. However, Non-Hispanic or Latino participants also prefer less polished designs on cultural products that are mostly consumed by a culture but prefer polished designed products on products that are not as culturally connected.

There is also a connection from both groups that an authentic product is less polished, looks cheap, has a homemade appearance, and has an older design.

Both groups of participants connected that a polished cultural product is bland, corporate, found at American brands such as Trader Joe's, Walmart, Shoprite, and Stop & Shop, and has an American look.

Limitations

This research was limited to a majority of participants having 16-18 years old. While there were some participants over the age of 16-18, assessing a larger age audience may have allowed the discovery of an age-related responses as older participants may have had more exposure to a culture. Increasing the participant size may have allowed for more patterns or more concrete results. Some participants did not complete all of the product forms, which led to some valuable data to not be attained.

Future Considerations

Having less questions with an easy-to-understand questions may lead for participants to respond with less ambiguity and reach more responses through the forms. Having less questions with easier language will allow for the use of necessary data only, as this research disregarded the answers of participants ethnicities and the parts of the products that influenced their choice were asked in multiple selection rather than an explanation. The data attained from that question was irrelevant to the research or its results.

Bibliography

Berlin Packaging. (2024). *Minimalism: Design Considerations to Ensure Less Is More*.

<https://www.berlinpackaging.com/content/market-insights/2024-Minimalism-Trends.pdf>

Fessenden, T. (2021, January 24). *Aesthetic and minimalist design*. Nielsen Norman Group.

<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/aesthetic-minimalist-design/>

Hsiao, E. (2024, March 13). *Why is the world losing color?* Medium. [https://uxdesign.cc/why-is-the-](https://uxdesign.cc/why-is-the-world-losing-color-56f740f465d4)

[world-losing-color-56f740f465d4](https://uxdesign.cc/why-is-the-world-losing-color-56f740f465d4)